

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B171
Date: 13 Feb 2006
Take Off: 08:49:11
Landing: 13:06:56
Flight Time: 4h17m45s

Campaign: DODO
Trials Instructions: Biomass / Aerosol Sampling
Operating Area: North of Dakar, over ocean

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Roberts	Directflight
3	CCM	Jackie Mulholland	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Hugh Coe	University of Manchester
5	Flight Manager	Alan Woolley	FAAM
6	VACC/PAN/WAS	Jim McQuaid	University of Leeds
7	AVAPS	Paul James	FAAM
8	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
9	Filters	Alison Perry	FAAM
10	AMS 2	Gerard Capes	University of Manchester
11	Wet Neph	James Bowles	Met Office
12	Core Chemistry	Ruth Purvis	FAAM
13	SWS/SHIMS	Ian Rule	Met Office
14	ARIES	Alan Vance	Met Office
15	Mission Scientist 2	Simon Osborne	Met Office
16	Engineer	John Kitchen	Avalon Aero
17	CVI/CCN/CCM2	Jamie Trembath	FAAM
18			

Flight Track:

B171 Track 13-FEB-06

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b171

Date: 13 Feb 2006

Project: DODO

Location: Dakar-Nouadhibou

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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083548		inu to nav	0.02 kft	338	
083609		engine start	0.02 kft	338	
083854		power change	0.02 kft	338	
084048		taxy start	0.02 kft	338	
084222		asp open	0.02 kft	105	
084258		start tapes	0.02 kft	105	
084911		T/O	0.02 kft	353	from dakar
085146		zero nevzorov	3.2 kft	343	
085808	092726	Profile 1	13.4 - 24.0 kft	334	started at takeoff 240 kts @ 090804
092944		bbrs exposed	24.0 kft	329	
094803		sonde 1	24.0 kft	329	launch
100547	102133	Profile 2	24.0 - 5.2 kft	346	
101557		tapes change	11.7 kft	002	
102133	102855	Run 1	5.2 - 5.0 kft	011	profile2 end / run1 start
102146		Run 1.1	5.0 kft	011	
102906	103108	Profile 3	5.0 - 4.0 kft	012	500ft/min
103108	104037	Run 2.1	4.0 kft	346	500ft/min
103319		bbrs exposed	4.0 kft	340	
104042	104823	Profile 4	4.0 - -.20 kft	350	500ft/min at 3000 ft
104834	105205	Run 3.1	-.15 - -.16 kft	010	
105212	105502	Profile 5	-.16 - 1.2 kft	057	
105511	112323	Run 4.1	1.2 kft	055	
110945		heimann cal	1.2 kft	013	qnh = 1025mb
112323	112416	Profile 5	1.2 - 0.72 kft	033	
112417	114658	Run 5.1	0.72 - 0.71 kft	033	
114708	115122	Profile 7	0.71 - 4.7 kft	094	
114913		tapes change	2.2 kft	082	
115135	121450	Run 6.1	4.7 kft	090	
121458	122036	Profile 7	4.7 - 0.74 kft	174	
122037	125219	Run 7.1	0.74 - 0.76 kft	175	qnh 1022 @1246
125229	125548	Profile 9	0.77 - 5.0 kft	180	
125928		asp closed	5.0 kft	154	
130656		Land	-.13 kft	016	at Nouadhibou
131209		standstill	-.11 kft	040	20'55.75N, 17'02.00W

B171 Track 13-FEB-06

FAAM Sortie Brief

DODO: dust in-situ sampling and radiation studies

Flight No: B171

Date: 13th February 2006

Trial objectives:

To perform in-situ microphysical and chemical measurements of Saharan dust aerosol over the ocean.

Location:

Over sea areas between point A (22°00'N, 20°00'W) and point B (24°00'N, 20°00'W)

Weather:

High loadings of atmospheric dust. Cloudless skies preferred.

Special requirements:

Re-fuel at Nouadhibou.

Flight pattern:

1. Take off from Dakar.
2. Profile to FL240 at 1000ft/min heading north [25mins, T=25mins]
3. Transit at range speed towards point A via GUNET [45mins, T=70mins]
4. Profile descent at science speed from FL240 to FL050 at 1000ft/min to reach point A [20mins, T=90mins]
5. SLR at FL050 heading north [20mins, T=110mins]
6. Profile descent from FL050 to 50ft towards point B at 1000ft/min above 3000ft and at 500ft/min below 3000ft [10mins, T=120mins]
7. Carry two 10min SLRs at 100ft on reciprocal headings orientated north-south [25mins, T=145mins]
8. Carry out a 15min SLR at two different levels within the dust plume orientated north-south (suggest 2000ft and FL050) with profile climbs between the levels [40mins, T=185mins]
9. Carry out a 15min SLR at two different levels within the dust plume orientated east-west (suggest 2000ft and FL050) with profile climbs between the levels [40mins, T=225mins]
10. Profile descent to 600ft [10mins, T=235mins]
11. Perform four orbits at maximum angle of bank at 600ft altitude [10mins, T=245mins]
12. Profile to FL150 at 1000ft/min towards Nouadhibou [10mins, T=255mins]
13. SLR at FL150 to Nouadhibou [45mins, T=300mins]
14. Land Nouadhibou.

Re-fuel

15. Take off from Nouadhibou.

If further science required:

16. Profile to FL150 at 1000ft/min towards point B [15mins, T=15mins]
17. SLR at FL150 [20mins, T=35mins]
18. Profile descent from FL150 to reach point B at 50ft at 1000ft/min above 3000ft and at 500ft/min below 3000ft [20mins, T=55mins]
19. Carry out SLRs within the dust plume [35mins, T=90mins]
20. Profile ascent to FL240 at 1000ft/min heading south [20mins, T=110mins]
21. Transit at high speed to Dakar [70mins, T=180mins]
22. Land Dakar.

Else:

Transit direct to Dakar.

Mission Scientist's Debrief Sheet

Flight B171

13th February 2006

Summary of the weather conditions:

Large area of well developed cumulus streets to the north of Dakar stretching to 25 N, aligned with the BL wind blowing from 40 N. Overhead, clear skies for much of the time. It was cloudless to the east over the Mauritanian Coast and inshore waters with a little cirrus coverage. The cumulus cover appeared to diminish through the afternoon.

Scientific Aims;

The flight aimed to locate and sample a dust storm, which was predicted by the CAM and NAME models to be advecting dust from northern Mauritania and Western Sahara westwards over the eastern Atlantic in the operating region to the north of Dakar.

Points defined:

Dakar airfield (13°29'N, 2°10'E). 700ft elevation; GUNET 19° 35' 42N 19° 44' 6W; Point A 22°00'N, 20°00'W, Point B (24°00'N, 20°00'W), Nouadibou (20° 55' 59N 17° 1' 48W)

Summary of the flight:

The forecast predicted the dust to be situated a considerable distance to the north of Dakar and so after an initial profile to FL240 a transit at range speed was carried out before conducting a profile descent to point A. A sonde was released north of GUNET, immediately before descent into point A. Considerable cumulus cloud (6/8), a significant fraction of which was developing congestus. The aerosol in this region was very low in concentration and marine in nature. Some clear air slots to the north were identified and these were targeted. Heading to the NNW to find a clear slot, a short profile determined that there was little dust but as the model prediction was for low level outflow sampling at 1000' under the cloud layer was carried out. Close to point B there were a few scattered and light showers. A northerly run was continued to the 25°N limit of operation and then survey work to the east was continued to establish if the dust was further to the east. Cloud was prevalent for the first half of this easterly leg though dissipated to towards the coast. Some evidence of a low concentration sulphate layer in the marine boundary layer was seen but no evidence of dust. A profile established the complete absence of dust and the aircraft continued at 5000' towards Dakhla, before heading southwards, parallel to the coast to Nouadibou. The only evidence of dust was observed on descent into Nouadibou with scattering coefficients around 100 Mm^{-1} and evidence of large particle scattering. To the west there was visible evidence of a pollution layer at the top of the marine boundary layer.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.171A**
FAAM © 2004

Date 13/2/2006

Page 1 of 2

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
Pre Takeoff					T18, 118° P1016 mbar
08:49	T10				TRANSIT TO GUNET AT RANGE SPEED 6-7/8 CIRRUS IN AREA. Decision to drop speed at GUNET still in order to get pe dist Bank was at FLO50 Zero Thr Mantr at #100'
09:48:03		FL240	329	19.4N 19.6W	DROPSPEED REVERSED CLOSE TO GUNET
10:05:27	PROF1	FL240	346	20.9N 19.5W	Begin profile 1 descent to FLO50
10:21:46	END P1 START RUN1	FLO50	14	22.0N 19.5W	
10:28:59	END RUN1	FLO50			Considerable strat developing
10:29:06	START PROFILE 2	FLO50 → FLO40			Need to slow to find clear sat cloud remains at low level but
10:31:08	RUN1	FLO40	346	22.6N 19.5W	clear at FLO40. Profile descent show v little aerosol near nose >30mm ² and CO 150 ppb. C-beaks
	RUN2	end run			
10:40:42					Dist to level so descend to FLO30 under the strat C _u
10:47:20					Showers v scattered
10:48:23	PROF				
10:48:32	RUN3.1	100 ft		23.5N 20W	
10:52:05	RUN3.1	100 ft		23.5N 20W	
10:52:12	PROFILES	→ 1500 ft		23.6N 20W	
10:55:02	PROFILES	1500 ft			end profile
10:55:02	RUN4.1	1500 ft			
10:55:45					ICAP inc ~100 particles 50 inc but <100
11:21:00					Extended westerly run will continue on a 30° heading to reach the 25W limit available
11:23:23	end RUN4.1	1500 ft → 1000 ft	33	24.9N 18.9W	then due east (Hdg 91°) towards coast to do a survey to see if there are tabs.

11:24:11
start
profile 6
end profile 6

24.9N 18.9W

coast to do a survey to
see if there are tabs.

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG FOR FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight Number : B171

Date : 13/2/06

Operator and contact info :Ruth Purvis rupu@faam.ac.uk

Problems with Instruments

CO	none
O₃	none
NO_x	None
SO₂	N/A
TDLAS	None
WAS	N/A

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B171

Date: 13/02/06	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 06:45:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
08:49:11																Start Profile 1 from Takeoff	
08:51:40	50	0.11	0													FL030	
08:52:16	15	0.09		Fail												FL040	
08:52:48	70	0.09														FL050	
08:53:40	70	0.09														FL060	
08:54:20	80	0.09														FL070	
08:54:52	50	0.09														FL090	
08:56:13	10	0.09														FL110	
08:57:00	10	0.09		Restart												FL120	
08:57:47	7	0.09														FL130	
08:58:42	7	0.13														FL140	
08:59:17	5	0.11														FL150	
09:00:18	3	0.14														FL160	
09:01:16	6	0.14														FL170	
09:01:49	10	0.13														FL180	
09:02:39	5	0.14														FL190	
09:03:33	6	0.14														FL200	
09:04:32	6	0.14														FL210	
09:05:44	9	0.15														FL220	
09:06:51	5	0.15														FL230	
09:08:04	10	0.14														End of Profile 1 @ FL240	
10:05:51	25	0.07														Start Profile 2 from FL240	
10:06:44	25	0.08														FL230	
10:07:32	Noise															FL220	
10:08:27	Noise															FL210	
10:10:54	25	0.08														FL180	
10:11:46	20	0.08														FL170	
10:12:40	20	0.08														FL160	
10:13:15	20	0.08														FL150	
10:13:57	25	0.08														FL140	
10:14:45	20	0.10														FL130	
10:15:36	22	0.11														FL120	
10:16:35	20	0.11														FL110	
10:17:35	8	0.11			Noise											FL100	
10:18:25	8	0.10			Noise											FL090	
10:19:15	18	0.10														FL080	
10:20:03	9	0.09														FL070	
10:20:52	12	0.10		1												FL060	
10:21:47	60	0.09		5	1											End of Profile 2 & Start Run 1 @ FL050	
10:22:00	50	0.09		10	2												
10:24:00	45	0.09		20	2												
10:26:00	40	0.09		5	1												
10:28:00	50	0.09		5	1												
10:28:55																End of Run 1	
10:29:10																Start Profile 3 From FL050	
10:31:08																End of Profile 3 & Start Run 2 @ FL040	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B171

Date: 13/02/06	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 06:45:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 2 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
10:32:00	150	0.08	0	30	3												
10:34:00	150	0.08		10	1												
10:36:00	140	0.09		30	3												
10:38:00	160	0.08		20	4												
10:40:38																End of Run 2 & Start Profile 4 from FL040	
10:41:53	260	0.08		20	5											FL030	
10:43:23	285	0.08		20	5											FL020	
10:45:13	290	0.09		30	8											FL010	
10:48:27	330	0.09		40	8											End of Profile 4 @ 50'	
10:48:45																Start Run 3 @ 100'	
10:49:00	270	0.09		30	8												
10:51:00	280	0.09	Off	40	5												
10:52:06																End of Run 3 & Start Profile 5 from 100'	
10:55:03																End of Profile 5 & Start Run 4 @ 1500'	
10:56:00	230	0.09	Off	60	10												
10:58:00	270	0.09	Off	70	10												
11:00:00	290	0.09	Off	80	10												
11:02:00	250	0.09	Off	60	10												
11:04:00	260	0.09	Off	60	10												
11:06:00	300	0.09	Off	50	10												
11:08:00	350	0.09	Off	50	8												
11:10:00	310	0.09	Off	50	8												
11:12:00	290	0.09	Off	50	4												
11:14:00	300	0.09	Off	40	5												
11:16:00	350	0.09	Off	70	10												
11:18:00	400	0.09	Off	80	10												
11:20:00	340	0.09	Off	90	10												
11:22:00	360	0.09	Off	90	10												
11:23:16																End of Run 4 & Start Profile 6 from 1500'	
11:24:20																End of Profile 6 & Start Run 5 @ 1000'	
11:25:00	480	0.09	Off	60	10												
11:27:00	420	0.09	Off	60	Noise												
11:29:00	500	0.09	Off	60	Noise												
11:31:00	530	0.09	Off	60	10												
11:33:00	560	0.09	Off	60	Noise												
11:35:00	600	0.10	Off	70	Noise												
11:37:00	600	0.10	Off	70	Noise												
11:39:00	580	0.10	Off	70	Noise												
11:41:00	550	0.10	Off	60	10												
11:43:00	550	0.10	Off	60	10												
11:45:00	400	0.10	Off	60	10												
11:46:59																End of Run 5 & Start Profile 7 from 1000'	
11:49:05	330	0.10	1	60	10											FL020	
11:49:48	260	0.10	4	10	Noise											FL030	
11:50:36	75	0.10		10	Noise											FL040	
11:51:28																End of Profile 7 & Start Run 6 @ FL045	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B171

Date: 13/02/06 **Operator:** MAP **DRS Time:** 06:45:00 **DAU1 Time:** +0 **DAU2 Time:** +0 **DAU3 Time:** +0 **Aux1 Time:** +0 **Aux2 Time:** +0 **Page 3 of 4**

G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
11:52:00	100	0.10	Off	10	10												
11:54:00	140	0.10	Off	10	Noise												
11:56:00	80	0.10	Off	10	Noise												
11:58:00	90	0.09	Off	10	10												
12:00:00	70	0.09	Off	10	Noise												
12:02:00	100	0.10	Off	10	8												
12:04:00	100	0.10	Off	10	Noise												
12:06:00	90	0.10	Off	10	Noise												
12:08:00	90	0.10	Off	10	2												
12:10:00	80	0.10	Off	10	2												
12:12:00	85	0.10	Off	10	2												
12:15:00																End of Run 6 & Start Profile 8 from FL045	
12:15:45	80	0.09	4	10	2											FL040	
12:17:07	380	0.10		50	8											FL030	
12:18:50	450	0.10		50	8											FL020	
12:20:36																End of Profile 8 & Start Run 7 @ 1000'	
12:21:00	690	0.10		40	8												
12:23:00	700	0.09		40	10												
12:25:00	730	0.09		50	10												
12:27:00	730	0.09	Off	40	9												
12:29:00	680	0.09	Off	50	9												
12:31:00	750	0.09	Off	50	9												
12:33:00	770	0.09	Off	50	3												
12:35:00	740	0.09	Off	50	10												
12:37:00	770	0.09	Off	80	8												
12:39:00	750	0.09	Off	80	10												
12:41:00	735	0.09	Off	80	9												
12:43:00	700	0.09	Off	80	10												
12:45:00	675	0.09	Off	80	8												
12:47:00	700	0.09	Off	90	10												
12:49:00	700	0.09	Off	100	10												
12:51:00	620	0.09	Off	50	3												
12:52:25																End of Run 7	
12:52:34																Start Profile 9 from 1000'	
12:53:31	100	0.09	Off	10	1											FL020	
12:54:17	65	0.09	Off	5	1											FL030	
12:54:57	60	0.09	Off	5	1											FL040	
12:55:45	50	0.09	Off	5												End of Profile 9 @ FL050	
15:38:18	90	0.09	Off	5												Start Profile 10 from FL050	
15:40:58	100	0.10	Off	5												FL040	
15:42:55	100	0.10	Off	10	Noise											FL030	
15:45:10	100	0.09	Off	10	Noise											FL020	
15:49:58																End of Profile 10 & Start Run 8 @ 100'	
15:50:00	130	0.09	Off	20	Noise												
15:52:00	310	0.08	Off	20	Noise												
15:54:00	145	0.09	Off	20	Noise												

CLLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B171 (called B171A in the cloud physics logs)

Date:

B) FFSSP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to PC	X	
Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data	X	
Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt	X	
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to the directory	X	
PMSDATA: on FLOODS	X	
3) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS	X	
a) Flight number: Bnnn	X	
b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX	X	
c) Output directory: PMSDATA:	X	
d) Start time: 0 if unknown	X	
e) End time: 240000 if unknown	X	
4) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT	X	Note the calibration file used
a) Flight number: Bnnn	X	
b) Directory: PMSDATA:	X	
c) TAS in processing: Y	X	
d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0	X	
e) Calibration file: Use the most recent calibration file.	X	
Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt	X	CAL27022006.TXT
Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]	X	Zero glitches
f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N	N	Yes only if gross errors occur
g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)	-	in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) In PVWAVE		
a) enter:		
!path=!path+',mrfb:[pms.proc]'		
Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important!		
b) write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat',	X	
'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto	X	
1st argument is output file from 5)	X	
2nd argument is the MFD	X	
3rd argument is the new FFSSP data file in M5 format	X	
c) exit	X	
6) MODIFY	X	
a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp	X	
b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX	X	
c) New dataset: Enter updated MFD name	X	
d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	X	
7) CHECKS:	n/a	
i) FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC – are they correctly synchronized in time?	No cloud	
ii) If not, may be necessary to repeat 5b) using addt=x keyword. This adds x sec to FFSSP time.		
iii) Alternative at 5b) is to use ,auto=602 or auto=605 to align FFSSP with Nevzorov LWC or TWC.		

CLLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B171 (B171A in cloud physics logs)

Date:

C) 2D PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC	X	
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)	X	
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS	X X	
4) Log on to FLOODS	X	Condor
5) unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.zip	X	B171A+B171B in zip file (use B171A only here)
6) In PVWAVE	X	Note the number of bad block reads and/or final numbers of blocks read & written
i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]'	X	No bad blocks
ii) CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE	X	
a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.dat	X	B171A.DAT
b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] Bnnn_seadas.dat		
iii) exit	X	B171_SEADAS.DAT
7) run MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE	X	Don't worry about lots of FORTRAN run-time errors as long as the program continues. These are format errors when writing to ascii files.
a) Default directory: PMSDATA:	X	
b) Flight number: Bnnn	X	
c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] Bnnn_seadas.dat	X	
d) Comment string:	X	
e) Start time: 0 if unknown	X	
f) End time: 240000 if unknown	X	
g) Read 2DC: Y	X	
h) Read 2DP: Y	X	
i) Secondary data Y	X	
j) FSP-SYNC: Y	X	
k) cmd.str: Y	X	
l) Auto time correction: N	X	
m) Full length secondary: N	X	
8) 2D image display and printing		This section is optional
Quick look at image blocks if required		
In PVWAVE		
i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]'		
i) WAVE> IMAGEDISPLAY		
a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA:		
b) Flight number: Bnnn		
c) IWC plot: N		
d) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP		
e) Start time: 0 if unknown		
f) End time: 240000 if unknown		
g) Time interval (sec): 0 for every image block nominal 5 sec		Features to look for: 1) Noise on 2D-P – does it affect non-edge diodes (with potential to create spurious particle counts)? 2) Can you identify a dominant particle habit for the whole flight (eg. drops or crystals) 3)

Preparation of imagery for Core data product		
iii) WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time 0 if unknown e) Enter end time 240000 if unknown f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks 10		
iv) exit PVWAVE Creates files	PMSDATA:	FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_Bnnn_2Dx-IMAGES.PS
ftp *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC		
Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter		
Output as pdf file (70 dpi resolution) and append name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files		
9) run MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO	X	If program crashes at a certain Time, for any reason, re-run With that time as the new end.
a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: Hit enter d) Time correction: Time offset of the 2D data	X X X x	
e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both 0 unless either probe known to be faulty h) Start time: Take-off or 0 if unknown i) End time: Landing or 240000 if unknown j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown l) Coefficient choice: 2 m) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D	X X X 085500 130700 0.2 8 2 X	Look for realistic times in Flight Summary file or Cloud Phys operator log. Note the particle type
10) In PVWAVE i) enter: !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! ii) WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' iii) exit	 X X X	Note: This will run quicker if you specify correct start / end times at 9h) and 9j).
11) MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	X X X X	
12) CHECKS:		
i) Is 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC?	n/a	

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number: B171****Date:**

D) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing	X	
Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	X X	
2) run MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW	X	Note the min size channel Note the volume flow rate
a) Flight number: Bnnn	X	
b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT	X	
c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii)	X	
d) Minimum size channel: Default = 1 If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here	X	Channel 1
e) Calibration volume flow rate: Use the most recent value. Calibration files to be stored in ????? Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm ³ /sec	X	1.6 ml/sec
f) Time correction: Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9 d)	X	0
g) Start time: Take-off or 0 if unknown	X	Look for realistic times in Flight Summary file or Cloud Phys operator log.
h) End time: Landing or 240000 if unknown	X	
3) In PVWAVE		Note: This will run quicker if you specify correct start / end times at 2g) and 2h).
i) enter: !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]'		
Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important!		
ii) write_procpcasp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat' 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp'	X	
iii) exit	X	
4) MODIFY	X	
a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp	X	
b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfd	X	
c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name	X	MFDE
d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	X	

CLLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: Bnnn

Date: DD/MM/YY

E) NetCDF file preparation and ftp to BADC		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Run TAREXEC:MFD_BADC		
For inputs below, just press ENTER to use defaults		
a) MFD to convert: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX b) version number for BADC: r[0] c) Names file: TARDIS_ROOT:[CALTEXT.NETCDF]CP_NAMES.TXT d) Directory: [DATA_ROOT:[NETCDF]] e) File prefix: [core-cloud-phy_faam] f) File suffix: [] g) File for output: [core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_Bnnn.nc]		Defaults in [square brackets] As from 4c) above default NOT the default default default default Default name is generated
2) Ftp transfer to BADC		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - stage 1) creates two files: - core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_Bnnn.nc - core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_Bnnn.txt The *.txt file should be renamed to core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_Bnnn_descrip.txt but this cannot be done on VMS as the filename is too long You should do it if the file is first transferred to a PC, or after it has been uploaded to the appropriate "incoming" directory at BADC a) ftp ftp.badc.rl.ac.uk b) login with username and password c) cd /incoming/faam/campaign-processed-core d) copy *.txt file as ascii e) copy *.nc and *2D-IMAGES.pdf files as binary		

F) BACKUP PROCEDURES		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Backup the intermediate files created in PMSDATA:		
a) zip "-V" PMSDATA:Bnnn*. * outdir:Bnnn_PMSDATA.zip Note that the uppercase "-V" option is important to preserve the VMS file characteristics when files are restored from this zip file.		Note destination directory "outdir"

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number:** Bnnn**Date:** DD/MM/YY

A) Raw data transfer to BADC		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer raw data files from DVD to PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt Bnnn_FFSSP.raw Bnnn_FFSSP_House_1.hse etc.		
2) Zip these file on the PC -output file: core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_bnnn_rawffssp.zip		
3) Transfer SEADAS Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC		
4) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip) - rename Bnnn.zip to core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_bnnn_rawseadas.zip		
5) ftp to BADC a) ftp ftp.badc.rl.ac.uk b) login with username and password c) cd incoming/faam/campaign_raw d) bin e) put core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_bnnn_rawffssp.zip f) put core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_bnnn_rawseadas.zip		Binary data transfer

CCN LOG

ALLEVIATOR GMT ON	OFF	HEIGHT	TEMP INLET	STATIC					REMARKS
				1	2	3	4	5	
10:13:38	24:08	5000ft	66	1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
			20.08	0.18	0.3	0.52			S
			18.94	79	296	404			D
			18.17	205	209	212			B
				2483	2481	2478			R
				1007.0	1007.0	1006.7			P
10:31:29	32:10	4000ft	66						S
			19.19	0.19	0.33	0.51	0.75	1.13	D
			218.98	287	513	434	5914	873	B
			18.22	228	230	230	233	246	R
			17.44	2434	2419	2412	2402	2397	P
			16.40	1013.6	1013.4	1013.4	1013.4	1013.4	
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
10:49:29	0:49:57	100ft	120.55	0.19					S
			0	432					D
			0	244					B
			4	2356					R
			5	1026.5					P
10:55:48	10:56:26	1500ft	1.20.5	0.18	0.33	0.51	0.74	1.12	S
			2.19.43	359	515	707	847	1385	D
			3.18.69	214	218	222	231	261	B
			4.17.91	2342	2337	2334	2332	2331	R
			5.16.9	1026.5	1026.5	1026.4	1026.4	1026.5	P
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
11:05:28	11:04:02	"	1.20.25	0.18	0.32	0.51	0.74	1.12	S
			2.19.55	377	505	825	865	1516	D
			3.18.8	222	221	224	229	275	B
			4.18.04	2330	2331	2329	2336	2341	R
			5.17.02	1026.5	1026.4	1026.4	1026.3	1026.5	P
11:10:23	11:10:56	"	1.20.39	0.18	0.32	0.52	0.75	1.11	S
			2.19.67	363	440	636	1198	1589	D
			3.18.93	208	207	213	218	278	B
			4.18.19	2345	2352	2358	2369	2370	R
			5.17.18	1026.4	1026.4	1026.4	1026.4	1026.5	P
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
11:17:10	11:17:45	"	20.48	0.18	0.33	0.51	0.74	1.11	S
			19.77	411	494	904	1317	2239	D
			19.05	208	235	240	266	355	B
			18.29	2384	2435	2444	2450	2454	R
			17.28	1026.4	1026.4	1026.5	1026.5	1026.4	P
11:24:20	11:24:56	1000ft	20.64	0.18	0.32	0.50	0.73	1.10	S
			19.95	439	706	1090!! _{os}	1431	1459	D
			19.22	240	248	247	267	361	B
			18.47	2447	2447	2440	2433	2442	R
			17.45	1026.4	1026.4	1026.4	1026.4	1026.4	P

CCN LOG

!!! - peak not found, but max seen

ALLEVIATOR GMT ON	OFF	HEIGHT	TEMP INLET	1	2	3	4	5	REMARKS
11:35:34	11:39:10	1000ft	76	1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	Run
			1 20.79	0.18	0.33	0.5	0.73	1.11	S
			2 20.06	508	771	1119	1530	1817	D
			3 19.3	246	256	264	281	366	B
			4 18.54	2428	2439	2436	2434	2429	R
			5 17.51	1026.4	1026.3	1026.4	1026.3	1026.3	P
11:40:35	11:41:11	"		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	Run
			1 20.85	561	776	1073	1550	2577	D
			2 20.13	259	265	284	300	420	B
			3 19.39	2443	2453	2462	2462	2463	R
			4 18.64	1026.5	1026.4	1026.4	1026.5	1026.4	P
			5 17.63						
11:53:13	11:53:50	500ft		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	Run
			20.29	411	491	509!!!	1633	1503	D
			19.62	220	224	226	243	349	B
			18.76	2426	2418	2412	2401	2389	R
			17.72	1009.1	1008.9	1008.9	1009	1009.0	P
12:00:54	12:01:31	"		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	Run
			21.00	0.18	0.32	0.50	0.74	1.11	S
			20.27	220	378	551	941!!!	1325	D
			19.52	213	213	220	234	275	B
			18.73	2384	2378	2370	2357	2343	R
			17.81	1008.9	1009.0	1009.0	1009	1008.9	P
12:20:52	12:21:30	1000ft		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	Run
			21.48	0.18	0.32	0.5	0.76	1.1	S
			20.8	740	913	1052	1538	2262	D
			20.03	239	247	271	274	402	B
			19.24	2324	2323	2325	2329	2333	R
			18.21	1025.4	1025.4	1025.4	1025.3	1025.3	P
12:27:58	12:28:31	1000ft		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	Run
			21.46	0.18	0.32	0.5	0.76	1.1	S
			20.8	554!!!	904	996	1604	1954	D
			20.04	231	241	252	326	402	B
			19.2	2334	2340	2344	2347	2350	R
			18.22	1025.5	1025.4	1025.4	1025.4	1025.4	P
12:36:02	12:36:37	"		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	Run
			21.47	0.18	0.32	0.5	0.72	1.1	S
			20.76	788	832	1406	1735!!!	2256	D
			20.02	257	240	252	282	391	B
			19.25	2349	2352	2355	2358	2359	R
			18.28	1025.3	1025.3	1025.3	1025.3	1025.4	P
12:45:29	12:46:03	"		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	Run
			21.6	0.19	0.31	0.5			S
			20.88	506	938 ⁷⁸⁰	1600!!!			D
			20.09	224	230	244			B
				2354	2387	2359			R
					1024.4	1024.2			P
				1624.4					

Silphite aerosol

Run
5.1
6.1
7.1
Run
AB000100

ARIES flight log

Flight: B171 a

Location: ~ Mainlandia

page 1 of 6

Date: 13-2-6

Operator(s): VANCE

Resolution: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Notes:

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	Comments
0630	Startup	B171								OK
063222	-	B171a	C	23N	N19	18	-187	19	CH1x1 (checking)	OK
063626	-	B171b	C	30.8	21N	18	-189.9	19	CH2x1 (")	OK
063851	-	B171c	C	30.6	N22	19	-190	19	1Rx1 (")	OK
064114	-	B171d	C	30	N22	19	-190	20	Z1x1 (")	OK
064308	-	B171e	C	31	N23	19	-190	20	N1x1 (")	OK
06		B171f	C	31	N24	19	-190	21	N1x5 (")	OK
[Shut down for copying/backing-up of files &c. — restart. OK]										
084911	T/O (PI)								(~ 5.6/8 alt cut)	B det gain 4 looks good on Z
091011		B171 G							(Playing w' shutter - looks like HBB sh. recovers in < 30 sec)	TAT 250K
0920	Transit									
092322	" FL240?	B171 H	C	71	31	1.5	-190	28	CH1x2	OK
092647	"	B171 I	C	71	31	1.5	-190	28	CH1x1	OK
092852	"	B171 J	O	71	31	0.2	-190	25	Z1x4 (OK)	clean above. Scattered ($\frac{1-2}{8}$) Gnd
093142	"	B171 K	C	71	30	-2.1	-190	21.7	CH1x1	
093316	"	B171 L	O	71	31	-1.7	-190	22	Z1x4 gain B:4	(TAT Tol -24, -39) OK
093717	"	B171 M	C	71	31	-3.2	-190	19	CH1x1	OK
093844	"	B171 N	O	71	31	-3	-190	20	Z1x4 G(2,4)	OK
094214	"	B171 P	C	71	31	-3.7	-190	18	CH1x1 G(2,2)	OK

ARIES flight log

Flight: B171 a

Location: Mauritania

page 2 of 6

Date: 13-2-6

Operator(s): VANCE

Resolution: 1

Gain A:

B:

Notes:

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shttr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	A GAIN B	Comments
094449	"	B171 Q	c/o	70	30	-4	-190	18	Z1x2	G(2,2)	OK
094725	"	B171 S	0	70	31	-5	-190	15	Z1x1	G(2,2)	OK
094847	"	B171 T	C	71	31	-5	-190	16	CH1x1	G(2,2)	OK
095040?	"	B171 U	C	71	31	-4			N1 x1	2+ 2	OK
095125	"	B171 *V	C	71	31	-4	-190	18	N1 x1	2- 2	OK
095227	"	B171 W	C	71	31	-5	-190	18	CH1x1	2 2	OK
095427	"	B171 X	C	71	31	-4	-190	19	CH1x1	2 2	OK
095538	"	B171 Y	c/o	71	31	-4	-190	19	Z1x2	2 4	OK
095738	"	B171 Z	0	71	31	-6	-190	15	Z1x1	2 4	OK
095853	"	B171 φ	C	71	31	-6	-190	15	CH1x2	2 2	OK
100112	"	B171 1	0	70	31	-6	-190	17	Z1x3	2 4	OK
100403	"	B171 2	C	71	31	-7	-190	15	CH1x1	2 2	OK
100517	"	B171 3	0	70	30	-7	-190	15	Z1x3	2 4	SP2, 100547 OK
102147	R1 Flow50	B171 4	C	71	30	2.5	-190	22	CH1x1	2 2	OK
102303	"	B171 5	0	71	30	6.3	-190	21	Z1x4	2 4	OK
102649	"	B171 6	C	71	31	10.9	-190	19.9	CH1x1	2 2	OK 1028 EoR
102803	" / p/R Flow40	B171 7	0	70	30	11	-190	20	Z1x4	2 4	running on. SR 2.1?
103216	R 2.1	B171 8	C	71	30	13	-190	20	CH1x1	2 2	OK
103333	"	B171 9	0	70	31	14	-190	21	Z1x4	2 4	(between A & B on chart)

ARIES flight log

Flight: *B171a*

Location: *Mauritania*

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Date: *13-2-6*

Operator(s): *VANCE*

Resolution: *1*

Gain A:

B:

Notes:

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	GAIN A/B	Comments
103720	R2-1	^C B 171a	C	71	31	15	-190	20	CH1x1	2 2	OK
103908	"	C171b	O	71	31	15	-190	21	Z1x1	2 4	(104040, EOR) OK
104021	ER	C171c	C	70	31	15	-190	21	CH1x1	2 2	OK
104836	R3-1, 100'	C171D	C	71	31	17	-190	23	CH1x1	2 2	OK
104950	R3-1	C171E	O	70	30	19	-190	23	Z1x3	2 4	EOR 105205 OK
105540	R4-1	C171F	O/C	70					CH1x1	2 2	OK
105707	R4-1	C171G	O	71	32	21	-190	24	Z1x4	2 4	OK
110101	R4-1	C171H	C	71	32	21	-190	23	CH1x1		OK
110300		ARIES I							Software restarted to close files		
110327	R4-1	C171J	C	71	31	21	-190	24	CH1x1	2 2	OK
110445	"	C171K	O	70	31	21	-190	24	Z1x3	2 4	OK
110744	"	C171L	C	71	32	21	-190	24	CH1x1	2 2	OK
110910	"	C171M	O	71	32	21	-190	24	Z1x3	2 4	OK
111207	"	C171N	C	71	32	21	-190	24	CH1x1	2 2	OK
111315	"	C171O	O	70	32	22	-190	25	Z1x3	2 4	OK
111623	"	C171P	C	71	32	22	-190	25	CH1x1	2 2	OK
111752	"	C171Q	O	71	32	21	-190	25	Z1x1	2 4	OK
111858	"	C171R	O	71	32	22	-190	25	Z1x1	2 4	OK
111958	"	C171S	O	71	32	22	-190	25	Z1x1	2 4	OK

14 min

ARIES flight log

Flight: B171a

Location: *Mannitonia*

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Date: 13-2-6

Operator(s): VANCE

Resolution: 1

Gain A: B:

Notes:

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	GAIN		Comments
										A	B	
112111	R4.1	C171T	C	71	32	22	-190	25	CH1x1	2	2	OK
112228	R4.1	C171U	O	71	33	22	-190	25	Z1x3	2	4	(EOR 102323) <i>Running on</i> OK
112545	R5.1	C171V	C	71	32	22	-190	25	CH1x1	2	2	OK
112705	"	C171W	O	71	32	22	-190	25	Z1x3	2	4	TAT 15° Td 14° OK
113014	"	C171X	C	71	33	22	-190	26	CH1x1	2	2	OK
113132	"	C171Y	O	70	33	22	-190	26	Z1x3	2	4	OK
113432	"	C171Z	C	71	33	22	-190	26	CH1x1	2	2	OK
113554	"	C171φ	O	71	32	22	-190	26	Z1x3	2	4	OK
113902	"	C171I	C	71	33	22	-190	26	CH1x1	2	2	OK
114015	"	C1712	O	70	33	23	-190	26	Z1x3	2	4	OK
114327	"	C1713	C	71	33	23	-190	26	CH1x1	2	2	OK
115605	R / 5000'	C1714	C	71	31	21	-190	28	CH1x1	2	2	OK
115728	"	C1715	O	71	32	20	-190	27	Z1x3	2	4	OK
120037	"	C1716	C	71	31	18	-190	26	CH1x1	2	2	<i>Noise 1GM p start</i> / OK
120147	"	C1717	C	71	31	18	-190	26	CH1x1	2	2	" / OK
120303 [?]	"	C1718	O	70	32	17	-190	25	Z1x3	2	4	OK
120621	"	C1719	C	71	31	17	-190	25	CH1x1	2	2	OK
120736	"	D171a	O	70	31	17	-190	25	Z1x3	2	4	OK
121033	"	D171b	C	71	31	16	-190	24	CH1x1	2	2	OK

ARIES flight log

Flight: B171a

Location: Mauritania

page 5 of 6

Date: 13-2-6

Operator(s): VANCE

Resolution: 1

Gain A:

B:

Notes:

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	GAIN		Comments
										A	B	
121205	R 5000'	D171C	0	71	32	11	-191	25	Z1x3	2	4	OK CoR 121450
121520		D171D	g/c	71	31	16.3	-191	24	CH1x1	2	2	OK
122046	R7.1/1000'	D171E	C	70	31	17	-190	26	CH1x1	2	2	OK
122207	"	D171F	0	71	30	18	-190	26	Z1x3	2	4	OK
122509	"	D171G	C	71	31	20	-190	25	CH1x1	2	2	OK
122635	"	D171H	0	71	31	20	-190	26	Z1x3	2	4	OK
122941	"	D171I	C	71	31	20	-190	25	CH1x1	2	2	OK
123055?	"	D171J	0	71	31	21	-190	26	Z1x3	2	4	OK
123415	"	D171K	C	71	31	21	-190	26	CH1x1	2	2	OK
123603	"	D171L	0	71	32	21	-190	26	CH1x1 Z1x3	2	4	OK
123907	"	D171M	C	71	31	21	-190	26	CH1x1	2	2	OK BORED...
124036	"	D171N	0	70	32	21	-190	26	Z1x3	2	4	
124327	"	D171O	C	71	32				fell over			file handles.
124629	"	D171P?	C	71	31	26	-190	27	CH1x1	2	2	OK
124750	"	D171R	0	70	31	21	-190	26.4	Z1x1	2	4	OK
125050	"	D171S	C	71	31	21	-190	26	CH1x1	2	2	} some V-mousey cold IGMs } but ran OK
125210?	"	D171T	C	71	31	21	-190	27	CH1x1	2	2	
1300	- shut down for refuelling.											
1521	Restart.											

ARIES flight log

Flight: 13171 b

Location: Mauritania

page 6 of 6

Date: 13-2-6

Operator(s): VANCE

Resolution: 1

Gain A: B:

Notes:

B171
↑
B172
↓

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	GAIN		Comments
										A	B	
153243	Rtn transit	D171V	c	71	31	24	-190	29	CHIX1	2	2	OK
		D172W	c									OK
1545:43	"	D172X	c	71	32	20.7	-190	25	CHIX1	1	8	oops!
1547:09	"	D172Y	o	70	32	22	-190	26	CHIX1			OK
1549:51	" R1	D172Z	c	71	33	23.6	-160	27	CHIX1	2	2	OK
1551:28	" 100'	D172φ	o	70	33	24	-189.9	27	Z1X3	2	8	OK
1554:11	"	D1721	c	72	33	24	-190	27	CHIX1	2	2	OK
1558:46	R2, 2000'	D1722	c	71	32	24	-190	28	CHIX1	2	2	OK
1600:43	"	D1723	φ	71	32	24	-191	28	Z1X5	2	8	Shutter opened ~160150/OK
1605:22	"	D1724	c	71	33	24	-191	28	CHIX1	2	2	OK
1608:03	"	D1725	o	70	34	24	-190	28	CHIX1	2	2	OK TAT 18 Td 7.5
1609:20	"	D1726	φ	70.7	33	24	-191	28.3	Z1X5	2	8	OK
1624		Pointing bits off to cool CBB end rad. science										

Flight leader nextgen
 then as B172 as warning
 to face with limited parameters
 Base set ARIES to B172 but
 can't turn it's with file allow
 to face B171 left off.

SWS and SHIMS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B171	Date	13/02/06	Operat or(s)	Ian Rule	log page	1	of	3
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Note to operator: Indicate whether entry refers to SWS or SHIMS

Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks	S W S	U S H	L S H
				Vis	NIR				

0748						SWS operated by rack pc, SHIMS by laptop. SHIMS nir appears to be working, but shutter does not. Box temp =20. Outboard peltiers appear u/s, resetting cut-outs does not work. Video recorder u/s			
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Note making zero cals with the current set-up (2 pc's), is easier if the shutters are closed using the interface card utility, therefore formal 'dark cals' will not be done as a matter of routine, the shutters just being closed for a period (these zero's will be obvious in the data, but the first and last zero measurement should be discarded). When the integration times for SWS are changed dark cals will be taken.

080801			90 aft	500	1000		x		
080920				500	2000	Nir shutter not working, vis dark measurement for 100s, box temp = 20		x	
084914						T/o Dakar, start profile, SWS pointing aft for t/o, SHIMS laptop packed away for t/o			
085200	P1		Zen+6 fwd	100	250	SWS start recording	x		
085625	P1			100	250	SHIMS start recording, 35 seconds of vis zero first. Box temp = 21		x	
090804		FL240				End profile			
091645	transit	FL240	Zen+6 fwd	100	250	Shutters closed for 30s on SWS and SHIMS vis. Some cloud above	x	x	
092252	"	"	"	500	1000	Integ time reset on SWS, patchy thin Ci above, box temp = 21	x		
093625						Shutters closed for approx 30s, box temp = 19, very clear above			
0937	"	"	Zen+6fwd	500	1000	Box temp varying between 17 and 20	x		
0937	"	"	-	100	250			x	
100547	P2	FL240				Start profile down			
100740						Shutters closed for approx 30s, box temp = 19			
10109			Zen+6 fwd	200	500	Reset sws integ time	x		
1020		~FL70		100	250	Entering very occasional cloud top		x	
102147	P2/R1	FL50				End profile and start run, box temp reached 16 (SHIMS nir still working)			
102855						End run shutters closed until 103015			
102906	P3					Start profile			
103109	P3/R2	FL40				End profile, start run			
1032	R2	FL40	Zen+6 fwd	200	500	In v occasional small Cu, clear above	x		
1032	R2	FL40	-	100	250	Box temp = 19		x	
104039	R2/P4					End run, start profile, shutters closed briefly			
104823						End profile, shutters closed briefly, sws integ time reset			
104834	R3.1	100'				Start run			
1049			Zen+6 fwd	100	500		x		
1049	R3.1	100'	"	100	250	Box temp = 17		x	
105207						End run			
105212	P5					Start profile			

SWS and SHIMS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B171	Date	13/02/06	Operat or(s)	Ian Rule	log page	2	of	3
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Note to operator: Indicate whether entry refers to SWS or SHIMS

Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks	S W S	U S H	L S H
				Vis	NIR				

105428			Zen+6 fwd	50	500	SWS integ time reset	X		
105503	P5/R4.1	1500'				In thin Cu, end profile start run			
1056				100	250	Box temp = 19		x	
110300	R4.1	1500'				Shutters closed for 15s, running under many small Cu SWS and SHIMS reacting very well and getting good signals	x	x	
111900						Shutters closed for 15s, box temp =20			
102323	R4.1/P6	1500'				End run, start profile, shutters closed in profile			
112416	P6/R5.1	1000'				End profile, start run			
1125	R5.1		Zen+6 fwd	50	500		X		
1125	R5.1			100	250			x	
1127						SHIMS NIR dropped out, box temp = 17		X	
1131						SHIMS stopped to reinitialise		X	
113124				75	250	SHIMS restarted nir ok, box temp = 19		x	
113400	R5.1	1000'				Shutters closed for 15s	x	x	
114559	R5.1/P7	1000				End run, start profile			
115122	P7	5000'				End profile			
115135	R6.1	5000'				Start run, at level of cloud tops			
1155	R6.1	5000'	Zen+6 fwd	50	500	Box temp = 19	X		
1155	"	"	"	75	250			x	
120430						Shutters closed for 15s			
1205	R6.1	5000'	Zen+6 fwd	50	500	Box temp = 19	X		
1205	R6.1	5000'	"	75	250			x	
121300	R6.1/P8	5000'				End run, start profile down, in haze layer, some small Cu			
122036	P8/R7.1	1000'				End profile, start run, some small Cu above, in haze			
123430						Shutters closed for 15s, box temp = 18			
1236	R7.1	1000'	Zen+6 fwd	50	500	Mostly clear above	X		
1236	"	"	-	75	250			x	
125220	R7.1/P9	1000'				End run, start profile			
125550		FL50				End profile			
125630						Shutters closed			
1258						Instruments off for landing			
1259						Laptop time = DRS minus 1 second			
130657						Land Nouadhibou			
152505						T/o Nouadhibou			

Note flight manager renamed flight to B172, hence 'either or' profile numbers. Standard parameters for this flight will be logged under B172

153851	P1 or P10	5000				Profile descent			
154035			Zen+6 fwd	50	500	Mirror in position	x		
1541	P1 or P10			75	250			x	
154400						Shutters closed for 15s, box temp = 17			
155000	R1 or R8	100'				End profile, start run			

Filter Sampling Log

Flight No:

B171

Date:

13 FEB 2006

Operator:

Type of filters mounted in	Top inlet	47 mm Whatman QMA (top)	Bottom inlet	90 mm 0.4 µm Nuclepore followed by a 90 mm paper (top)
Except for				

Run No	Disk #1 TOP	Disk #2 MIDDLE	Disk #3 BOTTOM	Inlet Top/ Bottom	Time On	Time Off	Flight Run	Accum Vol [l]	Comments
Filters run1	B171Q1	----	----	Top	10:55:00	11:38:00	R4.1/R5.1	6202	1.2 kft/0.72–0.71 kft, light loading
Filters run1	B171N1	----	----	Bottom	10:55:00	11:38:00	R4.1/R5.1	4040	1.2 kft/0.72–0.71 kft, light loading
Filters run2_a	B171Q2	----	----	Top	11:42:00	11:47:00	R5.1	746	0.72–0.71 kft, light loading
Filters run2_a	B171N2	----	----	Bottom	11:42:00	11:47:00	R5.1	493	0.72–0.71 kft, light loading
Filters run2_b	B171Q2	----	----	Top	12:20:00	12:49:00	R7.1	5604	0.74–0.76 kft, possibly dust
Filters run2_b	B171N2	----	----	Bottom	12:20:00	12:49:00	R7.1	4324	0.74–0.76 kft, possibly dust

All BC filters: foil was not replaced over stack after exposure

WAS Filling Log			
Operator - Jim McQuaid			
Date	Bottle#	Start	End
13/02/2006	47	10:26:50	10:27:50
13/02/2006	48	10:35:22	10:36:22
13/02/2006	33	10:39:24	10:40:24
13/02/2006	34	10:56:43	10:57:44
13/02/2006	35	11:05:46	11:06:46

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B** 171

Date: 13th February 2006

Instrument	Operated	Instrument	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>		<u>Cloud Physics</u>	
INU	Y	Probes	
XR5M GPS	Y	FFSSP	Y
Cruciform GPS	N	PCASP	Y
Satcom C	Y	2D-P	Y
Satcom H	Y	2D-C	Y
<u>Thermometers</u>		Cloudscope	N
De-Iced Temp	Y	SID 1	Y
Non De-Iced	Y	SID 2	Y
Heimann	Y	HVPS	N
<u>Hygrometers</u>		CIP25	N
G. Eastern	Y	CIP100	Y
J. Williams	N		
Nevzorov	Y		
TWC	Y		
FWVS	N	Racks:	
<u>Radiometers</u>		INC	N
Upper Clear	Y	CCN / CPC	Y
“ Red	Y	CVI	Y
“ Silicon	Y		
“ SHIMS	Y	<u>Aerosol</u>	
Lower Clear	Y	PSAP	N
“ Red	Y	Nephelometer	Y
“ Silicon	Y	Filters	Y
		AMS	Y
<u>Large Radiometers</u>			
TAFTS	N		
MARSS	N		
DEIMOS	N	<u>Others:</u>	
ARIES	Y	NIR TDLAS	N
SWS	Y	2BT O3	N
<u>Chemistry</u>		VACC	Y
Ozone	Y	PEROXIDE	N
SO2	Y	Formaldehyde	N
NOX	Y	ADA	N
CO	Y	CPI	N
ORAC	N	NOxy	N
PAN	Y	PTRMS	N
PERCA	N	Bag Sampling	N
WAS	Y	Tube Sampling	N

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B171

Date: 13 February 2006

Instruments

1. Upper and Lower Pyrometers – signal noisy
2. JW not operated
3. No
- 4.
- 5.

Aircraft

Nil

Satcom Calls

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B171:

Log	Reason
Wet Nephelometer	No Wet neph logs exist for B171 - Simon Osborne
CVI	No log is ever taken for CVI
AMS	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM
VACC	No log is taken/provided for VACC
PAN	No log is taken/provided for PAN

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x Forward Facing Cameras
3 x Downward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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